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MODERN TRENDS AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES**

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MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA’LIMI VAZIRLIGI**

**GULISTON DAVLAT PEDAGOGIKA INSTITUTI
XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA**

**FILOLOGIYA VA TIL TA’LIMI:
ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR**
2025-YIL 23–24-OKTABR, GULISTON DAVLAT PEDAGOGIKA INSTITUTI

**МИНИСТЕРСТВО ДОШКОЛЬНОГО И ШКОЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН**

**ГУЛИСТАНСКИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ
ИНСТИТУТ
МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ**

**ФИЛОЛОГИЯ И ЯЗЫКОВОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ:
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“O‘zbekiston Respublikasi **Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi** tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida” O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 5847-sonli Farmonida ko‘zda tutilgan vazifalardan biri – ilmiy izlanish yutuqlarini amaliyotga joriy etish yo‘li bilan fan sohalarini rivojlantirish, ya’ni xalqaro ilmiy hamjamiyatda e’tirof etilishiga xizmat qilishdir. Shu va boshqa tegishli farmonlarda va qarorlarda belgilangan vazifalarni amalga oshirish maqsadida **2025 yil 23–24 oktyabr** kunlari Guliston davlat pedagogika institutida

“FILOLOGIYA VA TIL TA'LIMI: ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR”

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya o‘tkazilgan. Konferensiya zamonaviy pedagogika va filologiyaning eng dolzarb ilmiy mavzularini aks ettirishga qaratilgan.

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

Assalomu alaykum Xurmatli Mehmonlar, aziz ustozlar! Mamlakatimiz bugungi kunda jahon hamjamiyati ko‘z o‘ngida barcha sohalarda jadal rivojlanib bormoqda. Shu o‘rinda barcha tarmoqlar va sohalarda, eng avvalo, ta‘lim sohasi, sog‘liqni saqlash va qishloq xo‘jaligida keng islohotlar joriy etish bo‘yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Jumladan, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 5 oktyabrdagi PF 6079-son “Raqamli O‘zbekiston – 2030” strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risidagi Farmoni, 2024-yil 2 fevral kuni PQ-54-son “Ta‘lim sohasidagi islohotlarni jadallashtirish bo‘yicha qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida”gi Qarori, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 19.01.2022-yil 19-yanvardagi 34-son “Xorijiy tillarni o‘rganishni takomillashtirish bo‘yicha qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida”gi Qarori qabul qilindi. Mazkur farmon va qarorlar milliy ta‘lim sohasini yanada rivojlantirish, chet tillarni chuqur o‘rganish, bugungi O‘zbekiston imijining, uning dunyo arenasidagi nufuzining oshiishiga xizmat qilishi shubhasiz.

So‘nggi yillar davomida yoshlarni bugungi kun talabiga mos holda tarbiyalash, chet tillarni chuqur o‘rganish, bugungi yoshlarning kamida ikkita chet tilini mukammal bilishlariga qaratilgan tadbirlar davlat miqyosida amalga oshirilmoqda. Shuning uchun ham kun tartibiga ta‘lim transformatsiyasi sharoitida tillarni o‘qitish muammolari va istiqbollarini ta‘minlashdek dolzarb masala ko‘ndalang qo‘yilmoqda. Global axborot jamiyati shakllanayotgan davrda ta‘lim va tillarni o‘qitish masalalari milliy taraqqiyot, har bir fuqaroning mamlakat kelajagi uchun ijtimoiy faolligi va mas‘uliyati, mamlakatning dunyo miqyosidagi nufuzining oshishini ta‘minlovchi muhim omildir.

Guliston davlat pedagogika institutida o‘tkazilayotgan “Filologiya va til ta‘limi: zamonaviy tendentsiyalar va innovatsion yondashuvlar” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiyasi soha mutaxassislarini ushbu masalani tadqiq etish, tillarni o‘qitish muammolari va istiqbollarini ta‘minlash, bu bo‘yicha olib borilayotgan yangi tadqiqotlar bilan tanishish, xorijiy tajribalarni o‘rganib, ularni amaliyotda qo‘llash, til o‘rganish madaniyatini shakllantirish bo‘yicha istiqboldagi islohotlarni chuqurlashtirish bo‘yicha taklif va tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqish, muammolarni zamonaviy yondashuvlar asosida tahlil qilish imkoniyatini berishi bilan ahamiyatlidir. Mazkur anjuman mamlakatimiz tadqiqotchilarining sa‘y-harakatlari natijasi bo‘lib, ushbu anjuman materiallari ta‘lim, fan, shuningdek pedagogika sohasidagi mutaxassislar malakasini oshirishga yordam beradi, degan umiddamiz.

Konferentsiya to‘plami ta‘lim jarayonining asosiy subektlari bo‘lgan pedagog va talabalar ehtiyojini hisobga olgan holda tuzilgan bo‘lib, aynan ustoz-o‘qituvchilar millionlab yoshlarning iqtidorini, shu jumladan, ta‘lim va tarbiya madaniyatini shakllantiruvchi asosiy shaxslar bo‘lib hisoblanishi bilan dolzarbdir.

Guliston davlat pedagogika instituti rektori
J. X. Karshibaev

tarixiy manba sifatida qadrlaydi va uni o'rta asr musulmon jamiyatlarining ma'naviy-ma'rifiy manzarasini tiklashda muhim vosita deb hisoblaydi. "Ahmad Yassaviy xalqqa din va tasavvufdan saboq berish maqsadida ular anglaydigan ravon, soda tilda hikmat aytdi",- deydi N. Hasan. Darhaqiqat, Ahmad Yassaviy xalqqa din va tasavvufdan saboq berishda o'z zamonasining ijtimoiy, ma'naviy va madaniy sharoitlarini chuqur anglagan holda, murakkab diniy-ta'limotiy tushunchalarni oddiy xalq qalbiga yetib boradigan ravon va sodda tilda bayon etishga intilgan. Uning hikmatlari inson ruhiyatiga yaqin, tushunarli, hayotiy masalalarga doir bo'lib, ko'pchilik tomonidan oson qabul qilinardi.

Yassaviy o'z hikmatlarida sof axloqiy qarashlarni ilgari surib, insonni ichki poklik, sabr-toqat, halollik, taqvo, xudbinlikdan voz kechish kabi qadriyatlarga chorlagan. U xalq bilan bir tilda so'zlashib, ularning dardini, ehtiyojini, saviyasini hisobga olib hikmatlar yaratgani bois, uning ta'limoti keng omma orasida chuqur ildiz otgan. Ahmad Yassaviy o'z ijodi orqali tasavvufni faqatgina zohiriy ilmlarga emas, balki botiniy tushuncha va ruhiy kamolotga asoslangan yo'l sifatida targ'ib etdi. U hikmatlar orqali nafaqat diniy bilim, balki axloqiy-ruhiy tarbiyani ham xalq ongiga singdirishga harakat qildi.

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DISTINGUISHING BETWEEN DIGITAL AND CYBER DIPLOMACY: A TERMINOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE IN ACADEMIC RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT. This article explores the challenges of terminology in the study of digital diplomacy. Current academic discourse remains fragmented, influenced by factors such as the emergence of new terms, shifting definitions, and limited continuity across different research phases. The analysis highlights how certain expressions-like "e-diplomacy" or "tweetplomacy"-have gradually fallen out of common use, though they still appear in some contexts worldwide. At the same time, terms such as "digital diplomacy," "cyber diplomacy," and "digital public diplomacy" have proven more stable and hold greater promise for future scholarly inquiry. To strengthen the field, the article recommends establishing a clear periodization, refining definitions, and integrating new concepts into

existing terminological frameworks. Based on this analysis, three main directions in the study of digital diplomacy are identified: the adoption of new technologies in diplomatic practice (including social media), the emergence of new negotiation agendas, and the intersection of computational sciences with diplomacy.

KEYWORDS: cyber diplomacy, data diplomacy, digital diplomacy, data diplomacy, science diplomacy, digital international relations

INTRODUCTION. The influence of digital technologies on diplomacy has emerged as an important area of research since the early 21st century, although earlier studies had already highlighted speculative possibilities for their application in diplomatic practice [1].

It should be emphasized that the information revolution of the late 20th century was not the first challenge requiring diplomats to adapt. Earlier, innovations such as the steam engine and the telegraph enabled continuous communication between diplomatic missions and decision-making centers, thereby reducing the range of issues on which diplomats could act independently. In a similar way, the rise of the internet, email, and social media further accelerated information exchange and expanded the volume of data processed by diplomatic services.

This process has given rise to a variety of new terms, *including media diplomacy, digitalization of public diplomacy, virtual diplomacy, hybrid diplomacy, e-diplomacy, cyber diplomacy, net diplomacy, public diplomacy 2.0, and real-time diplomacy.*

The proliferation of numerous definitions—often overlapping or embedded within one another—has resulted in terminological confusion. Certain terms failed to gain widespread acceptance because of their limited focus, being tied to specific platforms or functions, while others fell out of use due to the absence of clear and consistent definitions.

By contrast, terms like *digital diplomacy* and *cyber diplomacy* (along with their variations) have proven to be the most resilient within academic discourse. This paper aims to systematize the principal conceptual approaches to defining these terms and to highlight prospects for their further development, using *data diplomacy* as an illustrative case.

METHODOLOGY. This study employs a qualitative approach, combining discourse analysis and conceptual mapping to trace the evolution of terminology in the field of digital diplomacy. Academic works, monographs, and policy documents from the early 2000s to the early 2020s were reviewed, with attention given to both scholarly and governmental sources. The analysis focused on identifying the contexts in which terms such as *digital diplomacy*, *cyber diplomacy*, and related concepts were introduced, how their definitions have shifted over time, and the extent to which they have been integrated or abandoned in academic discourse. To capture broader trends, the material was thematically examined with reference to three directions of digital diplomacy studies: the integration of new technologies into diplomatic practice, the emergence of new negotiation agendas, and the intersection of diplomacy with computational sciences.

Since 2011, research on digital diplomacy has generally followed two main definitional approaches: broad and narrow. The narrow approach views digital diplomacy primarily as the use of digital technologies to shape foreign public opinion or to serve public diplomacy objectives [3]. This perspective highlights two central aspects: the focus on communication channels and efforts to influence public opinion. Accordingly, it mainly encompasses the use of social media platforms, such as Twitter, and official websites.

In turn, the broad approach is characterized by understanding digital diplomacy as the influence of digital technologies on diplomacy as a whole [4]. However, given that researchers have often refined their definitions over a relatively short period, it is currently

difficult to identify which approach is more characteristic of individual countries or institutions.

The broad definition put forward by Manor-like any expansive concept-necessitated further clarification. To address this, Oxford University researcher K. Bjola introduced a distinction between the micro- and macro-levels of digital diplomacy. At the macro level, digital diplomacy is situated within broader contexts such as networks and soft power, while at the micro level, it refers to the specific contributions of digital technologies to diplomatic practice, including consular services, crisis communication, and influence efforts [6].

At the same time, I. Manor, expanding the definition of digital diplomacy itself, proposed to speak separately about the digitalization of public diplomacy, referring to the use of social networks to promote the state image [5]. A similar position is held in one of her recent works by N. A. Tsvetkova, speaking separately about the digitalization of public diplomacy [7].

Some researchers address this issue by introducing the additional term "tweetplomacy" ("Twitter diplomacy"), which refers to the use of social media, primarily Twitter*, for public diplomacy and to improve a state's image. This term gained widespread popularity in the early 2010s [8], but is still used by researchers, especially outside the Western academic community. For example, several monographs devoted to this phenomenon, published in the Middle East, include "Twitter Diplomacy: Media Polarization Before and After the Abraham Accords" by Nayad Alsayed [9] and "Within Tweeting Distance: How States Use Twitter Diplomacy" by Nur Suwan [10].

The issue of terminology becomes even more complex with the parallel emergence of the term *cyber diplomacy*. It first appeared around the same period as *digital diplomacy*, notably in the 2002 collective volume *Cyber-Diplomacy: Managing Foreign Policy in the Twenty-First Century*, edited by Canadian scholar Evan H. Potter [11]. Similar to digital diplomacy, however, *cyber diplomacy* was introduced without a clear or consistent definition.

Potter's work initially defined it as conducting information campaigns through new technologies (the internet, websites), although the book also extensively explores the influence of media on diplomacy in general. Like digital diplomacy, cyber diplomacy in its current sense was popularized after 2011, when the term migrated into academic circles from US State Department reference materials.

The U.S. State Department's documents also refrain from offering a precise definition, but their description indicates that cyber diplomacy *covers a wide spectrum of U.S. interests in cyberspace, including cybersecurity, internet freedom, internet governance, military applications of the internet, innovation, and economic growth*. It is in this broader sense that the term has gained traction within the academic community.

Examples of cyber diplomacy in this sense include the work of the UN Open-Ended Working Group on Norms of Conduct in Cyberspace or negotiations aimed at resolving cyber incidents. This is well reflected in the fact that the term has become established, particularly within the UN, as well as the fact that the prefix "cyber-" is more often used in the context of security.

Later, S. Riordan defined cyber diplomacy as *the use of diplomatic tools and approaches to address issues arising in cyberspace*. To differentiate between digital and cyber diplomacy, a similar logic can be applied to that used by Russian researcher E. A. Konkov in his work *Digitalization of Politics vs. the Politics of Digitalization*. Konkov distinguishes between the digitalization of politics-as the integration of technology into political relations-and the politics of digitalization, which concerns political management of

digital technology development in the economy and social sphere [12]. In the context of diplomacy, this distinction translates into two dimensions: the integration of technology into diplomatic relations on the one hand, and *digitalization diplomacy*-the involvement of diplomats in shaping the emerging digital negotiation agenda-on the other.

Revising terminology and refining definitions makes it possible to link the key phenomena examined by contemporary digital diplomacy scholars with Dizard's original concept. However, this still leaves unresolved the boundary between digital diplomacy and digital public diplomacy, as well as the question of how newly emerging terms fit within this framework.

Thus, this field of academic inquiry remains fragmented in both its terminology and conceptual foundations for several reasons. First, scholars frequently adopt terms borrowed from official policy documents. Second, the meaning of the word *digital* has shifted significantly over the past decades. Third, the continuous emergence of new digital technologies and communication platforms has introduced additional terms into scholarly discourse, such as *tweetplomacy* [8] and *data diplomacy*.

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DIRECTIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE APPLICATION FOR SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT IN ASIMOV'S STORIES

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Abstract. Isaac Asimov's robot stories remain a cornerstone for understanding the philosophical, ethical, and technical challenges of artificial intelligence (AI). The author's formulation of the *Three Laws of Robotics* provided an early framework for machine ethics, governance, and human-AI cooperation. This article explores the directions of AI application for social development presented in Asimov's works, emphasizing how fictional depictions anticipate real-world AI research areas such as human-robot interaction, cognitive architectures, ethical decision-making systems, and AI-based governance models.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, robotics, Asimov, machine ethics, algorithmic governance.

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